

Design and Development of Secure Intelligent E-Court (SIEC) System

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Abstract

In this project, we investigate and identify the functional and nonfunctional requirements responsible for establishing and developing a successful electronic court system (SIEC). The court cases' performance will be evaluated using a survey of public users and staff, and then the existing e-court system will be analyzed. The need for an e-court system has become critical under rapid technology and work changes that enable users to check and track their case data without security or privacy issues.

We used unified modeling language (UML), including use-case diagram, class diagram, context diagram, and login activity diagram, to clarify the parties of the e-court. Moreover, we designed and implemented an e-court system using web programming languages such as Java, PHP, JavaScript, HTML, and CSS.

The proposed "SIEC" system was developed by initiating planning functional and nonfunctional requirements from stakeholders in the existing e-court system; these requirements will be identified using a standard well-defined usability questionnaire.

A total of 10 people in the Justice of Palace Court in Kuwait participated in the usability assessment. Accordingly, 60% of stakeholders mentioned improvements needed and 30% of users indicated an average rating.

Furthermore, we mentioned security measures to protect the integrity of court records and biometric authentication systems. Intelligent methods were incorporated, such as document analysis and case management electronically.

Keywords: e-court, portal of justice, cases performance evaluation, intelligence platform, security technique.

Chapter 1: Introduction

Advanced countries advise their work agencies with sensitive data to use e-portals with high security and privacy and consider this a top priority; for example, the e-court portal used by the Ministry of Justice. The system is created to provide judicial services electronically for stakeholders' users and achieve their work needs.

The current era with rapid inventions and technologies globally opens up new challenges of positive and negative points of the electronic web world that provides electronic services for users, such as enhancements in web apps. On the other hand, security or privacy gaps may lead to hacking and exposing important data in an organization, so that is why security is important in e-court. Several significant organizations mention the concept of a “green court” with less usage of papers, as they have become more concerned after the coronavirus pandemic period.

In Kuwait, the e-court exists now, but it is not separated from the web. It needs a custom platform design with multiple functions tools, more operation improvement, and high security and privacy with usability measures.

Moreover, we need to focus on and review the requirements of functionality list points because they are considered core elements before building and enhancing any system. Any illegal or cybercrime act will affect the e-court portal, such as cost and idle of the judicial body.

Any shortcomings in the preparation of requirements and documentation or in security will result in lower performance and damage to the primary server. As a result, intelligence and security are the primary arguments for enabling usability systems while protecting users' data.

1.1 Motivation

The motivation portion of the study on e-court aims to identify the desired objectives and facilitate discussions to determine the factors relevant to the users and stakeholders in an intelligent court system.

The following are the objectives behind creating an electronic court system:

- **Reduce the time and cost of litigation:** By automating many of the manual processes involved in the court system, involving electronic judicial services for users.

- **Increase transparency:** E-court systems can make court records more accessible to the public, which can help increase transparency and accountability in the judicial system.
- **Improve access to justice:** E-court systems can make it easier for people to access the courts, regardless of their location or socioeconomic status.
- **Reduce traditional papers:** By reducing the need for paper documents, e-court systems can help reduce the environmental impact of the court system.
- **Improve the functional and nonfunctional requirements** of the e-court system.
- **Design a user-friendly platform** with high security and intelligence.

Many sectors in various countries are transitioning from traditional methods to digital platforms, resulting in time savings and efficient archiving through digital means.

There are several advantages for the court in maintaining and safeguarding crucial documents, as well as preventing the loss of sensitive data. Additionally, this practice benefits court users by allowing them to access and stay informed about their cases through online platforms.

The use of an online system and the automation of court operations would result in enhanced efficiency for all parties involved in the court processes.

1.3 Problem Statement

A notable limitation is the absence of a tailored platform for e-court design, encompassing comprehensive control over users' case data, a user-friendly dashboard for online updates, and streamlined work management for stakeholders.

Thus, we need to build and secure an e-court platform to provide judicial services electronically that run with high efficiency and effectiveness while minimizing time-consuming procedures and costs. So, it is imperative to prioritize the maintenance and improvement of the existing and future infrastructure of the system to avoid any risk or issues that may threaten users' data files and deliver more system functions to satisfy all user's needs.

Furthermore, it is important to develop functionality and non-functionality requirements to effectively implement the e-court system by keeping in contact and interactively performing users' tasks.

1.4 Objectives

The objectives of this project are to design, develop, and maintain an e-court application that covers the following main features:

- Designing an e-court web app with effective usability.
- Delivering several judicial services smartly.
- Improving practices for avoiding user privacy and security issues.
- Saving time and reducing costs, more effectively than the traditional method
- Developing functional and nonfunctional needs.
- Developing intelligent case management for the stakeholder.

1.7 Methodology

Firstly, using questionnaire, we take function and non-function requirements of existing Kuwait e-court system. get functional and non-functional requirements from other researchers' work. identify the functional and nonfunctional requirements of our proposed system. incorporated strong security and intelligence then lastly, test the SIEC system.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter covers a critical analysis of previously published research on multiple topics. The literature review will summarize the important zones of researcher work, author contribution table, and functional support of references. As a result, we might identify the key existing shortcomings or differences and gain the knowledge that provides a framework for developing a research proposal.

2.1 Researcher Work

In this part, we will analyze recent related work to the secure intelligent court cases (SIEC) system:

1- Users engagement factors with e-court application conceptual framework [Year 2022 Ref.3]

This study increases our knowledge of the elements influencing users' participation in e-court applications. It studies the structural connections between readiness traits and electronic courts to create defense tactics and enumerates the key aspects of how users interact with the e-court

application. Human behavior, technological improvements, organizational structure, and legal concerns are the four types of factors.

2- The IPS method positively protects judicial data on e-court application in court [Year.2022 Ref.1]

To guard against data theft, user misuse, and hacking, the active e-Court program requires a new security mechanism. E-court users who have already registered are the intended audience. Preventative actions are needed to protect network security and data prevention systems (IPS) that acts as network traffic detector.

3- The role of artificial intelligence in forensic evidence presentation [Year 2022 Ref.24]

This research discussed how artificial intelligence could enhance the success and presentation of evidence. The author highlights the role of artificial intelligence in forensic evidence by technology.

4- A full-trial system for the smart court [Year 2022 Ref.5]

This study developed a system for building a smart court to help achieve more effective, fair, and understandable trial proceedings (FITS). Information extraction, evidence categorization, question development, dialogue summarizing, judgment prediction, and judgment document generation are just a few of the crucial activities we introduce in the proposed FITS.

5- Tracking the development of intelligent court system in China [Year 2021 Ref.22]

This work offered an intelligent court system in the era of big data. Chinese courts have been focusing on using big data technologies in the administration of the justice system. They tend to develop a high capacity of online court to hold cases and procedures.

6- The application of e-court as an effort to modernize the justice administration in Indonesia [Year 2020 Ref.20]

This article sought to provide legal services electronically through an application called e-court. This application is an embodiment of the electronic justice system, which has become a commitment of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia.

7- Artificial intelligence and DNA computing [Year 2007 Ref.18]

The computer community has shown much interest in DNA computing, a paradigm that is still relatively new, with enormous parallelism, which is a feature. This article clarifies some problems requiring a degree of cleverness or intelligence. It is at this juncture where DNA computing and artificial intelligence meet.

2.3 Comparison of Similar Existing Systems

Table 3 demonstrates the functional support of digital court in several references on similar existing systems. The following is a list of functional requirements mentioned in multiple publications, along with the extent of their functional support:

Table 1: Comparison of similar existing systems

#	Functional requirement	Ref 1	Ref 2	Ref 3	Ref 4	Ref 5	Ref 6
-	E-case filing		✓	✓			
-	Case management system	✓			✓	✓	✓
-	Contact link between agencies			✓			
-	Report of summary cases	✓	✓			✓	
-	Evidence analysis		✓				
-	Add and update the case	✓				✓	✓
-	E-pay	✓		✓	✓		
-	Manage and reduce the pendency of cases	✓					
-	Case tracking system	✓					✓
Total		7	4	3	2	3	3

Chapter 3: Functional and Nonfunctional Requirements of SIEC

3.1 Functional Requirements

These describes how the system will operate and perform required processes and demonstrates system behavior of production inputs/outputs.

Functional support requirements:

- **Access module:** For authorized users to log into the system and use their personal info/profile account.
- **Add and remove case:** For a user to make a new case or submit a judicial request or delete it.
- **Update case and summary report request:** For making updates.
- **Backup:** For coping all data files, whether using external backup like hard disk or internal like cloud computing or apps such as one drive.
- **Database:** For storing abd recording information about users.
- Bckup data periodically (e.g., date, report number, plaintiff, defendant, and case or court type)
- **Evidence collection:** A platform within the system to check and collect evidence and send it as a document to the court authority/specialist.
- **Intelligent:** includes some uses of AI fields within system.

3.2 Nonfunctional Requirements

The nonfunctional requirements describe the attributes and properties of a system, encompassing what is necessary and its ability to handle various aspects.

The following is a list of nonfunctional requirements in the system:

- **Security:** The system must be designed to prevent any unauthorized person from logging in, only allowing those who are assigned a password and configuration with a firewall.
- **Dynamically:** The system has the ability to adapt to different devices and changes in processes.
- **Usability:** The system shall be easy to use and clear for all users, including the admin account.

3.3 Proposed System (SIEC) Attributes

We designed a new or improved system that serves users more efficiently and covers their needs using the following key elements:

- More electronic judicial services.
- Dashboard accounts for users.
- Checking the progress of the decision and procedures of the case.
- User interface design improvements.
- Developing an integration system to connect the court and other related agencies.

3.3.4 Security of SIEC system

Security mechanisms in the proposed system of E-court are as follows:

Table 2: Security mechanisms.

Security mechanisms	Brief description
User registration	Users must finish the registration process by entering their identification details in order to gain access to the system.
Identity proofing	After receiving a complete registration request, the system checks new account requests against existing ones to avoid duplications.
User authentication	After proofing eligible users' identities, the system generates users' IDs. The system requests those users to provide authentication information.
Access control list	It provides an access mode depending on the user's role and the object to be accessed. Access mode may involve read, write, delete, create, and modify or limiting that.
Encryption	One of computer systems' most effective defense measures is encryption or cryptography. The diabetic system will use encryption to store data in encrypted form.
Backup and recovery	Planning for database backup and recovery provides adequate safeguards from data loss and software errors.
Database security	In database security, the best way to maintain confidentiality is to encrypt data during transmission.

Figure: Security against vulnerabilities

The figure shows the different security controls that can be used to protect against vulnerabilities. These controls include firewalls, intrusion detection systems, antivirus software, and data loss prevention systems. The important step is to identify the vulnerability by scanning unknown devices' access and perform necessary update.

Chapter 4: UML Diagrams of SIEC System

UML Diagrams

This chapter discusses unified modeling language (UML) within the system.

The diagrams are used in software engineering and are deemed a general modeling that aims to provide a standard way to visualize the design of a system. It is used to create static structure diagrams. The main purpose of UML diagrams is to help developers build systems that are easy to understand, modify, and maintain. Several types of UML diagrams serve different purposes.

We will examine several diagrams pertaining to intelligent secure of the court system (SIEC) as follows:

4.1 Use-Case Diagram of SEC System

Figure: Use case diagram

Above is a use-case diagram showing each stakeholder with their use-case option box. So, the actors use the system and the related use cases for each actor. Describes what the system does and how the actors use it in an interactive manner. Thus, the use-case diagram illustrates what system functions are performed for which actor.

4.2 Class Diagram

Figure: Class Diagram

This class diagram represents each section with its items listed on it.

The class diagram is a static form of a UML diagram that describes the structure of a system by showing the system's classes, their attributes, operations, and the relationships among objects.

The diagram above clarifies specifically three classes, namely, Court, Stakeholder, and User.

(One court may have many cases processing, one or more stakeholders may have one case or more, one or more stakeholders may relate with one court, and finally one admin court could control and edit one and more users.)

4.3 Login Activity Diagram

Figure: Login activity.

This diagram clarifies login activity of the user to the system. Every professional system has a login portal for user login activity. If the user has an account and enters the correct ID username and password, they will access properly. If not matched or the wrong access info was entered, the system will refuse user access or login because the user was not authenticated.

4.5 Flowchart Activity of SIEC System

Creating a flowchart for an e-court system involves mapping out the various processes and activities involved in handling legal cases electronically. Above is a generalized flowchart that outlines the key activities in an e-court system.

Chapter 5: Case Decision Assessment

5.1 Case Decision Assessment

In this condition, the stakeholders are employees in the court or related to it, where assessment is created based on their decisions, **such as** court administration, judge, plaintiff, lawyer, and prosecutor. “UNITED NATIONS Guidelines (Review of JUDGEMENT No.158)”.

Case decision assessment involves analyzing and evaluating a specific court decision in a particular legal case. It focuses on understanding the reasoning behind the decision, assessing its strengths and weaknesses, and evaluating its implications.

Decision assessment form:

#	Case type	Court	Stakeholder	Assessment
1	Civil case	Hawally court	Plaintiff	Satisfy with the decision
2	Social case	Alahmadi court	Defendant	Appeal of the decision
3	Commercial case	Jahra court	Witness	The witness gives his testimony
4	Criminal Case	DC Court	Prosecutor	The public prosecution defends the plaintiff in the case

Note that the assessment also includes the public and implications considerations—moreover, the clarity and fairness of the court decision and future application.

Here are the judges’ numbers and trial sessions of the cases.

Court No.	Judges	Trial session No.	Public presence on the court	Public assessment percentage
1	Two judges	3	Yes	Almost 80%
2	One judge	2	No	90%
3	Three judges	1	Yes	100%
4	One judge	2	Yes	70%

Several factors can be considered when assessing a legal case decision as follows: firstly, the legal framework within which the decision was made; secondly, the evidence that was presented to the court; third, arguments that were made by the parties involved; fourth, the reasoning of the court in reaching its decision; lastly, the impact of the decision on the parties involved and on society.

Chapter 6: SIEC System Implementation

This chapter of the project focuses on user interface and tools designed to create a user-friendly system and achieves some of the convenience levels in the usability of the e-court system for all stakeholders.

Then, this section demonstrates coding and features required of the system to be integrated into web applications involving international metrics of building and use.

6.1 Development Tools

This chapter explains the developed web app of the court case system, which shows the several tools assisted in building, where the stakeholder could access and control their account and add/delete/edit cases or search bars or even use them to send judicial requests (sending and receiving).

6.1.1 Web application development

Webapp refers to a web application, a software application that runs on web browsers. It is designed to be accessed and used over the internet through a web browser, such as Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or Microsoft Edge.

Web applications utilize a client-server architecture, where the client refers to the web browser on the user's device, and the server refers to the remote computer or network that hosts the application. The web browser acts as the interface for the user to interact with the application, while the server handles the processing and storage of data.

Web applications can provide various functionalities, from simple tasks like displaying information and forms to more complex operations like handling e-commerce transactions, social media platforms, collaborative tools, and online banking systems. They are typically built using a combination of programming languages, such as HTML, CSS, and JavaScript for client-side (front-end) development and server-side technologies like PHP, Python, Ruby, or Java for back-end processing.

There are several development tools used during establishment e-court web app project as follows:

XAMMP: It stands for Cross-Platform (X), Apache (A), MariaDB (M), PHP (P), and Perl (P). It is a lightweight Apache distribution that makes it extremely easy for developers to create a local server for testing and deployment purposes. It includes server application (Apache), database (MariaDB), and server scripting language (PHP).

MySQL: It is a relational database management system (RDBMS). MySQL was used because of its consistently fast performance, high reliability, and ease of use.

PhpMyAdmin: It is a method of creating database table.

BROWSERS: It is a computer program with a graphical user interface for displaying HTML and PHP files. The following browsers are Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, and Opera.

Bluehost: It is a hosting and domain services provider that provides several options to control web app of the e-court system with a main control panel.

It may reserve the domain and host all of my webpages with their file sources to keep and backup on—running and providing support 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.

It uses some security plugins and monitoring site tools to protect the website on this side, like test connection and spam prevention and sending security alerts.

On the other hand, an SSL certificate should give and check the website address, including <https://>, because any vulnerabilities will allow the hacker an offside access to the data sources that may be considered sensitive and has privacy, then definitely be destroyed.

6.3 E-Court Web App screenshots

A website was created called E-court with a reserved domain and host. **We will list some screenshots of the website and explain each one as following:**

6.3.1 User registration page

This page is dedicated to enabling users/stakeholders to be members of the web app platform and get control and also create a new profile account on this system.

The registration form consists of a header with 'Login' and 'Sign Up' buttons. Below are four input fields: 'Username', 'Email', 'Password', and 'Confirm Password'. A checkbox labeled 'I accept the Terms of Service and Privacy Policy' is located below the password fields. A large black 'SIGN UP' button is at the bottom.

Figure: Registration page.

6.3.3 Admin dashboard control

The screenshot shows an admin dashboard with a sidebar menu on the left containing items like Tickets, Custom CSS & JS, Formidable, KB Articles, Creative Mail, Elementor, Templates, ElementsKit, Appearance, Plugins, Users, All Users, Add New, Profile, Tools, Settings, and ACF. The main content area features a notification for OptinMonster and a user management table. The table has columns for Username, Name, and Email, and includes bulk action buttons like 'Bulk actions', 'Apply', and 'Change role to...'. The user list includes:

Username	Name	Email
<input type="checkbox"/> Khaled	—	khaledym@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/> mbk0.mohamed	—	mbk0.mohamed@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/> Moawia	—	moawia.mabrouk@yahoo.com
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosad	—	Mohamed.mbk1@hotmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/> scotpedigo24	—	sheritaabigail@savedaday.com
<input type="checkbox"/> test1067670	—	test1067670@mail.imailfree.cc

Figure: Admin dashboard control on user's accounts

6.3.4 Court cases management system

Court Case Management System

Create New Case

Case Number:

Case Type:

Case Date:

List of Cases

Case Number	Case Type	Case Date
12345	Civil	2022-01-01

Figure: Case management system.

This system shows the search of the user-posted cases or the created new case by inserting the required information in the court case management system.

6.3.5 Submit new case

Stakeholders who are interested register new cases against a person or company.

Plaintiffs and defendants can insert personal data and information about another party by selecting the court name and case type and applying other fields like uploading documents and signatures.

Case registration

Note: user dude, apply for send your case information please.

Your Name *

Write your name

Insert Civil ID No. *

Select Case type *

Case No. *

Enter your case no.

Court name *
 Hawaii Court
 Alahmmadi Court
 Palace of Justice Court
 Jahra Court

Phone *

Enter your phone No.

Against: *

upload file

Any concerned document

Chapter 7: Proposed System Usability Evaluation

7.1 Proposed System Usability Evaluation

This chapter will discuss a usability questionnaire created by both public users and stakeholders of the e-court in Kuwait specifically created for the Ministry of Justice and Palace of Justice Court.

It contains statistical feedback on how effective the usability and intelligent the electronic court of Kuwait portal usage.

The information gathered and analyzed in this area regarding users was used to learn about local facts relating to developing the e-court system and serving/fulfilling user needs.

7.2 Questionnaire Report

It demonstrates the statistical percentage of usability questionnaire of user's responses created in Kuwait (Palace Court) regarding Kuwait e-court usability, taking a sample of 20 persons; the results are as follows:

According to the chart above, the usability rating of the e-court of Kuwait is shown, where perfect evaluation reported by 30% is considered the moderating percentage.

A good rate is only 10%, which is a weak and lower rate. Moreover, 60% indicated bad and need enhancing about the system.

Overall, the inference is that the highest rate by users, around 60%, refers to the need to enhance the system of the e-court platform in Kuwait.

7.2.1 Usability Test Results of SIEC system

We created an online survey by SUS platform (system usability scale), where around 20 users of our SIEC system participated in it as usability test. Its role is to check and improve the user experience toward the web app, consisting of multiple tools and templates.

Below is the question category used in the questionnaire for users' participation in SIEC web app system.

Question Category: System Usefulness, Overall Satisfaction, Information Quality, and Interface Quality.

- **System usability test results are as follows:**

	Out of 8 Rating
System Usefulness	8
Overall Satisfaction	8
Information Quality	8
Interface Quality	7.90
Average Percentage = 797.5%	

- **The calculation method that expresses in average percentage is as follows:**

$$(8 + 8 + 8 + 7.50) / 4 = 31.90 / 4 = \mathbf{7.975}$$

$$\text{Multiply by 100: } 7.975 \times 100 = \mathbf{797.5\%}.$$

Chapter 8: Conclusion and Future Work

8.1 Conclusion

Life is unpredictable, and electronic courts are essential for judicial services. Converting from traditional to digital work will help stakeholders process cases more efficiently. Enhancing electronic courts with intelligent attributes is crucial for a more reactive and efficient system. Robust security measures must be implemented to prevent network snooping and maintain data integrity. The proposed e-court system in Kuwait requires enhanced user interface and functionality based on a local usability questionnaire. This will provide flexibility and assist tools within the e-court platform, benefiting both users and staff.

8.2 Future Work

Technology improvements are anticipated to significantly impact the legal system in the future. There are some crucial areas where technology is likely to have a significant impact on how the justice system develops in the future; for example, technological advancements are expected to significantly impact the legal system in the future. Artificial intelligence (AI) can revolutionize case handling, online dispute resolution (ODR), and evaluating judgment rates from law datasets. Blockchain technology can enhance security and transparency, while chatbots can be trained on datasets to answer user questions. Cloud computing offers secure computing resources in conjunction with e-court systems, ensuring cost-effective collaboration and data security.

References

- [1] Afzal Sayed Munna & Syarifah Farrah Rizka Putri, "The IPS Method Positively Protect Judicial Data on e-Court Application in Supreme Court Indonesia". book: Compilation of Research. March 2022. Publisher: Notion Press.
- [2] Lisfer Berutu , Edy Lisdiyono , Sigit Irianto " E-Court System In Realizing Simple, Fast And Low-Cost Civil Justice: Learning From Indonesian Experience". Journal of Positive School Psychology. 2022, Vol. 6, No. 7, 2805-2819.
- [3] Adham M. M. Alankar, "Users Engagement Factors with e-Court Application Conceptual Framework". In book: Proceedings of the Future Technologies Conference (FTC) 2022, Volume 3 (pp.59-68) Oct. 2022.
- [4] Laud randy Amoah. "Electronic court case management system". January 2022.
- [5] Wei, B., Kuang, K., Sun, C. et al. "A full-process intelligent trial system for smart court". Front Inform Technol Electron Eng 23, 186–206 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1631/FITEE.2100041>
- [6] Wan Satirah Wan Mohd Saman. " Electronic Court Management System in Malaysia: The Legal and Functional Requirements for Court Records". in book: E-Systems for the 21st Century (pp.131-170). May 2016.
- [7] Arsalan Ali , Ibrahim Khalil " Role of Non-functional Requirements in projects' success" May 2022. DOI:10.1109/ICoDT255437.2022.9787463
- [8] Richard Susskind " Online Courts and the Future of Justice". November 2019.
- [9] Chawinga Chaupe "An evaluation of electronic case management system (ECMS) in the judiciary of Malawi: a case study. September 2017."
- [10] BOB WILY, consultant – "Judicial case management information system (CMIS) assessment. 18 Mar 2017."
- [11] Bharath Padmanabhan "Unified Modeling Language (UML) Overview" -2012.
- [12] Wan Satirah Wan Mohd Saman. " Electronic Court Management System in Malaysia: The Legal and Functional Requirements for Court Records". in book: E-Systems for the 21st Century (pp.131-170). May 2016.
- [13] Straton Papagiannas "A Review of the Chinese Scholarship on Building Smart Courts and Automating Justice" May 2021.
- [14] Nurussobah Hussin and Rusnah Johare "Functional Requirement Development For The Management Of Electronic Court Records In The Superior Court Of Malaysia". March 2016
- [15] George Yee, "Measuring Privacy Protection in Web Services". Journal. International Conference. October 2006. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICWS.2006.87>
- [16] Md Aminur Islam "Online Legal Service: The Present and Future". DOI:10.5121/ijcsit.2018.10502
- [17] Mohammad Ikbal Hasan "Virtual Court System during COVID-19 Pandemic". July 2021 DOI:10.35877/454RI.daengku385
- [18] Zoheir Ezziane "Artificial Intelligence and DNA Computing" DOI:10.1007/978-1-84628-943-9_10
- [19] Maja Brkan and Evangelia "Courts, Privacy and Data Protection in the Digital Environment" DEC 2017.
- [20] Pratiwi, S. J., Steven, S., & Permatasari, A. D. P. (2020) The Application of e-Court as an Effort to Modernize the Justice Administration in Indonesia: Challenges & Problems. Indonesian Journal of Advocacy and Legal Services, 2(1), 39-56. <https://doi.org/10.15294/ijals.v2i1.37718>
- [21] James E. McMillan and J. Douglas Walker "A Guidebook for Electronic Court Filing" 1998.
- [22] Hamid Mukhtar "Tracking the Development of Intelligent Court System in China". – Sep 2021
- [23] Maja Brkan and Evangelia "Courts, Privacy and Data Protection in the Digital Environment" DEC 2017.

- [24] Altayari, W., Kamalrudin, M., & Jaber, M. M. (2022). "The role of artificial intelligence in forensic evidence presentation." *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 6(S2), 5649–5662.
<https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS2.6429>
- [25] D. V. Soundari, P. N, P. R. K G and P. C. N M, "E-Court Management System," 2022 8th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS), Coimbatore, India, 2022, pp. 1118-1123, doi: 10.1109/ICACCS54159.2022.9785083.
- [26] Ugo Erra, Nicola Capece, Francesco Banterle. "Collaborative Visual Environments for Evidence Taking in Digital Justice. June 2021. Pages 33–37 <https://doi.org/10.1145/3452369.346382>
- [27] Salleh Bin Rosman, Ahmed A. A. Shehab. "Evaluation of the Case Management System in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) Judicial System". Vol 55, No 3 (2020).
- [28] Elena G. Popkova, ISC 2019: "Modern Global Economic System: Evolutional Development vs. Revolutionary Leap", p1541–1549.
- [29] Yara F. Naser Eldeen, "E-Court: The Symbolic Token of the 21st Century", 2020.
- [30] UNITED NATIONS Guidelines (Review of JUDGEMENT No.158).